

Some Theorems in Fuzzy Number Graceful Labeling Graphs

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Abstract: Certain idea about the fuzzy number graceful labeling graph of a fuzzy graph is given and some related concepts of the fuzzy number graceful labeling graph are also discussed.

Keywords: Fuzzy set, fuzzy graph, fuzzy number graceful labeling, fuzzy bistar graph, fuzzy wheel graph.

INTRODUCTION

First, fuzzy set had been introduced by Zadeh [16]. Succeeding years, fuzzy set was grown in different ways. The following are extension of fuzzy set, they are vague set, intuitionistic fuzzy set, bipolar valued fuzzy set and etc. In 1975, fuzzy graph was introduced by Rosenfeld [10], with modification of fuzzy graph was introduced by Arjunan.K and C.Subramani[2] and it was extended to many area. In similar way, [3], [4], [5], [6], [7], [8], [9], [11], [12], [13], [14] and [15] were useful to write this paper. K.Arjunan et al.[1] have given an idea about the fuzzy number graceful labeling graph. In this paper, graceful labeling is generalized, particularly fuzzy number graceful labeling, the triangular fuzzy number is used in this paper but we have different types of fuzzy number.

1. PRELIMINARIES

Definition 1.1. [16] A fuzzy set \tilde{N} on the given universal set Q is a set of ordered pairs $\tilde{N} = \{(x, F_m(x)): x \in Q\}$, where $F_m: Q \rightarrow [0,1]$, is called membership function.

Definition 1.2. [16] The k – cut of a fuzzy set \tilde{N} , is defined by $\tilde{N}_k = \{z: F_m(z) \geq k\}$, where $k \in [0, 1]$.

Definition 1.3. [16] Let Φ, Θ be two fuzzy subsets of a set G . The following relations and operations are defined as:

- (i) $\Phi \subset \Theta$ means $\Phi(t) \leq \Theta(t)$, for all $t \in G$.
- (ii) $\Phi = \Theta$ means $\Phi(t) = \Theta(t)$, for all $t \in G$.
- (iii) $\Phi^c(t) = 1 - \Phi(t)$, for all $t \in G$.
- (iv) $\Phi \cap \Theta = \{\langle t, \min(\Phi(t), \Theta(t)) \rangle / t \in G\}$.
- (v) $\Phi \cup \Theta = \{\langle t, \max(\Phi(t), \Theta(t)) \rangle / t \in G\}$.

Definition 1.4. [14] A fuzzy subset of the real line \mathbb{R} , whose membership function F_m satisfies the following situation, is a generalized fuzzy number \tilde{N}

- (i) F_m is a continuous mapping from \mathbb{R} to the closed interval $[0, 1]$,
- (ii) $F_m = 0, -\infty < x \leq a_1$,
- (iii) $F_m = L(x)$ is strictly increasing on $[a_1, a_2]$,
- (iv) $F_m = W_N, a_2 \leq x \leq a_3$,
- (v) $F_m = R(x)$ is strictly decreasing on $[a_3, a_4]$,
- (vi) $F_m = 0, a_4 \leq x \leq \infty$,

where $0 < W_N \leq 1$ and a_1, a_2, a_3 and a_4 are real numbers. Moreover, this kind of generalized fuzzy number is denoted as $\tilde{N} = (a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4; W_N)_{LR}$ when $W_N = 1$, it can be simplified as $\tilde{N} = (a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4)_{LR}$.

Definition 1.5. [14] The fuzzy set $\tilde{N} = (a_1, a_2, a_3)$, where $a_1 < a_2 < a_3$ and described on \mathbb{R} , is called a triangular fuzzy number, the membership function of \tilde{N} is given by

$$F_m = \begin{cases} \frac{x - a_1}{a_2 - a_1}, & a_1 \leq x \leq a_2 \\ \frac{a_3 - x}{a_3 - a_2}, & a_2 \leq x \leq a_3 \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Definition 1.6. The collection $S = \{ \tilde{0}, \tilde{1}, \tilde{2}, \dots \}$ of triangular fuzzy numbers is called non-negative triangular fuzzy numbers if $\tilde{a} = (a_1, a, a_3)$, $\tilde{a} \in S$, $a_1, a_3 \geq 0$. For example $\tilde{1} = (0, 1, 2)$ and $\tilde{0} = (0, 0, 0)$.

Definition 1.7. [11] The function principle was introduced by Shan-Huo Chen [10] to treat fuzzy arithmetical operations. This principle is used for the process for addition, subtraction, multiplication and division of fuzzy numbers.

Suppose $\tilde{N} = (a_1, a_2, a_3)$ and $\hat{U} = (b_1, b_2, b_3)$ are two triangular fuzzy numbers. Then

(i) the addition of \tilde{N} and \hat{U} is $\tilde{N} + \hat{U} = (a_1 + b_1, a_2 + b_2, a_3 + b_3)$, where $a_1, a_2, a_3, b_1, b_2, b_3$ are any real numbers.

(ii) The multiplication of \tilde{N} and \hat{U} is $\tilde{N} \times \hat{U} = (a_1 b_1, a_2 b_2, a_3 b_3)$, where $a_1, a_2, a_3, b_1, b_2, b_3$ are all non zero positive real numbers.

(iii) $-\hat{U} = (-b_3, -b_2, -b_1)$, the subtraction of \hat{U} from \tilde{N} is $\tilde{N} - \hat{U} = (a_1 - b_3, a_2 - b_2, a_3 - b_1)$, where $a_1, a_2, a_3, b_1, b_2, b_3$ are any real numbers.

(iv) $\frac{1}{\hat{U}} = \hat{U}^{-1} = (\frac{1}{b_3}, \frac{1}{b_2}, \frac{1}{b_1})$, where b_1, b_2, b_3 are all non zero positive real numbers, then the

division of \tilde{N} and \hat{U} is $\frac{\tilde{N}}{\hat{U}} = (\frac{a_1}{b_3}, \frac{a_2}{b_2}, \frac{a_3}{b_1})$.

(v) For any real number K ,

$K \tilde{N} = (K a_1, K a_2, K a_3)$ if $K > 0$

$K\tilde{N} = (Ka_3, Ka_2, Ka_1)$ if $K < 0$.

Definition 1.8.[14] (i). Defuzzification of $\tilde{N} = (a_1, a_2, a_3)$ can be done by Graded Mean Integration Representation Method. It is defined as

$$G(\hat{N}) = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\int_0^1 l[a_1 + l(a_2 - a_1) + a_3 - l(a_3 - a_2)] dl}{\int_0^1 l dl} = \frac{a_1 + 4a_2 + a_3}{6}.$$

(ii). [3] The signed distance of \tilde{N} is defined as

$$d(\hat{N}, 0) = S(\hat{N}) = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^1 a_1 + l(a_2 - a_1) + a_3 - l(a_3 - a_2) dl = \frac{a_1 + 2a_2 + a_3}{4}.$$

(iii). Total Integral Value Method (TI) of \tilde{N} is defined as

$$TI(\hat{N}) = \int_0^1 a_1 + l(a_2 - a_1) + a_3 - l(a_3 - a_2) dl = \frac{a_1 + 2a_2 + a_3}{2}.$$

Definition 1.9. [2] Let Φ be a FS in a set G . The strongest fuzzy relation Ψ is an ordered pair $\Psi = \{ \langle (c_1, d_1), \Psi(c_1, d_1) \rangle / c_1, d_1 \in G \}$ on G which is a fuzzy relation on Φ and is defined by $\Psi(c_1, d_1) = \min\{\Phi(c_1), \Phi(d_1)\}$ for all $c_1, d_1 \in G$.

Definition 1.10. [2] Let S be any nonempty set and L be any set with a function $\mathfrak{S}: L \rightarrow S \times S$. Then Φ is a ${}_F S$ of S , R is a fuzzy relation on S with respect to Φ and Θ is a ${}_F S$ of L such that $\Theta(e) \leq R(x, y)$. Then the ordered triple $\Omega = (\Phi, \Theta, \mathfrak{S})$ is called a fuzzy graph

(${}_F G$), here the elements of Φ are fuzzy points or fuzzy vertices (${}_F V$) and the elements of Θ are fuzzy lines or fuzzy edges (${}_F E$) of the ${}_F G$ Ω . Let $\mathfrak{S}(a) = (c_1, d_1)$. Then $(c_1, \Phi(c_1))$, $(d_1, \Phi(d_1))$ are adjacent ${}_F V$ s and $(c_1, \Phi(c_1))$, ${}_F E$ $(a, \Theta(a))$ are incident with each other. Let two distinct ${}_F E$ s $(a_1, \Theta(a_1))$ and $(a_2, \Theta(a_2))$ are incident with a common ${}_F V$. They are called adjacent ${}_F E$ s. Let $\Phi^* = \{ w \in S / \Phi(w) > 0 \}$ and $\Theta^* = \{ c \in L / \Theta(c) > 0 \}$. Then $\Omega^* = (\Phi^*, \Theta^*, \mathfrak{S})$ is a crisp graph.

Definition 1.11. [2] Let $\Omega = (\Phi, \Theta, \mathfrak{S})$ be a ${}_F G$. A ${}_F E$ is called a fuzzy loop (FL) if its end ${}_F V$ s of the ${}_F E$ are joined with same ${}_F V$.

Definition 1.12. [2] Let $\Omega = (\Phi, \Theta, \mathfrak{S})$ be a ${}_F G$. Then the ${}_F G$ Ω is called a fuzzy simple graph (${}_F S G$) if it has neither fuzzy multiple lines nor ${}_F L$ s.

Example 1.13. Consider the ${}_F G$ $\Omega = (\Phi, \Theta, \mathfrak{S})$, here $S = \{ a_1, b_1, c_1, d_1, e_1 \}$, $L = \{ x, y, z, u, v, w, p \}$ and $\mathfrak{S}: L \rightarrow S \times S$ is defined by $\mathfrak{S}(x) = (a_1, b_1)$, $\mathfrak{S}(y) = (b_1, b_1)$, $\mathfrak{S}(z) = (b_1, c_1)$, $\mathfrak{S}(u) = (c_1, d_1)$, $\mathfrak{S}(v) = (c_1, d_1)$, $\mathfrak{S}(w) = (d_1, e_1)$, $\mathfrak{S}(p) = (a_1, e_1)$. A ${}_F S$ $\Phi = \{ (a_1, 0.5), (b_1, 0.4), (c_1, 0.6), (d_1, 0.7), (e_1, 0.3) \}$ of S . A fuzzy relation $R = \{ ((a_1, a_1), 0.5), ((a_1, b_1), 0.4), ((a_1, c_1), 0.5), ((a_1, d_1), 0.5), ((a_1, e_1), 0.3), ((b_1, a_1), 0.4), ((b_1, b_1), 0.4), ((b_1, c_1), 0.4), ((b_1, d_1), 0.4), ((b_1, e_1), 0.3), ((c_1, a_1), 0.5), ((c_1, b_1), 0.4), ((c_1, c_1), 0.6), ((c_1, d_1), 0.6), ((c_1, e_1), 0.3), ((d_1, a_1), 0.5), ((d_1, b_1), 0.4), ((d_1, c_1), 0.5), ((d_1, d_1), 0.7), ((d_1, e_1), 0.3), ((e_1, a_1), 0.3), ((e_1, b_1), 0.3), ((e_1, c_1), 0.3), ((e_1, d_1), 0.3), ((e_1, e_1), 0.3) \}$ on S with respect to Φ and a ${}_F S$ $\Theta = \{ (x, 0.3), (y, 0.2), (z, 0.1), (u, 0.4), (v, 0.5), (w, 0.15), (p, 0.25) \}$ of L .

Fig. 1.1

In figure 1.1, (i) $(a_1, 0.5)$, $(b_1, 0.4)$, $(c_1, 0.6)$, $(d_1, 0.7)$ and $(e_1, 0.3)$ are FVs .

(ii) $(x, 0.3)$, $(y, 0.2)$, $(z, 0.1)$, $(u, 0.4)$, $(v, 0.5)$, $(w, 0.15)$ and $(p, 0.25)$ are FES .

(iii) $(a_1, 0.5)$ $(b_1, 0.4)$, $(b_1, 0.4)$ $(c_1, 0.6)$, $(c_1, 0.6)$ $(d_1, 0.7)$, $(d_1, 0.7)$ $(e_1, 0.3)$ and $(e_1, 0.3)$ $(a_1, 0.5)$ are adjacent FVs .

(iv) For example, $(x, 0.3)$ join with $(a_1, 0.5)$ and $(b_1, 0.4)$, so it is incident with $(a_1, 0.5)$ and $(b_1, 0.4)$.

(v) $(x, 0.3)$ and $(p, 0.25)$ are adjacent FES .

(vi) $(y, 0.2)$ is a FL .

(vii) $(u, 0.4)$ and $(v, 0.5)$ are fuzzy multiple edges.

(viii) The given F_G is not a FSG .

(ix) The given F_G is a FPG .

Definition 1.14. [2] Let $\Psi = (\rho, \sigma, \mathfrak{S})$ and $\Omega = (\Phi, \Theta, \mathfrak{S})$ be two F_G s of G . Then $F_G \Psi$ is called a fuzzy subgraph (F_SuG) of Ω if $\rho \subseteq \Phi$ and $\sigma \subseteq \Theta$.

Definition 1.15. [2] Let $\Omega = (\Phi, \Theta, \mathfrak{S})$ be a F_G . Then the degree of a fuzzy vertex is defined by $d(\beta)$ and $d(\beta) = \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{S}^{-1}(\alpha, \beta)} \Theta(a) + 2 \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{S}^{-1}(\beta, \beta)} \Theta(a)$.

Definition 1.16. [2] The minimum degree of the $F_G \Omega = (\Phi, \Theta, \mathfrak{S})$ is $\delta(\Omega)$, $\delta(\Omega) = \min\{d(\beta) / \beta \in S\}$ and the maximum degree of Ω is $\Delta(\Omega)$, $\Delta(\Omega) = \max\{d(\beta) / \beta \in S\}$.

Definition 1.17. [2] Let $\Omega = (\Phi, \Theta, \mathfrak{S})$ be a F_G . Then the order of Ω is defined to be $o(\Omega)$, $o(\Omega) = \sum_{\beta \in S} \Phi(\beta)$.

Definition 1.18. [2] Let $\Omega = (\Phi, \Theta, \mathfrak{S})$ be a F_G . Then the size of Ω is defined to be $S(\Omega)$, $S(\Omega) = \sum_{a \in \mathfrak{S}^{-1}(\alpha, \beta)} \Theta(a)$.

Definition 1.19. [5] A $F_G \Omega = (\Phi, \Theta, \mathfrak{S})$ is called fuzzy regular graph if $d(\beta) = r$, for all $\beta \in S$. It is also called a fuzzy r – regular graph.

Definition 1.20. [5] A $F_G \Omega = (\Phi, \Theta, \mathfrak{S})$ is called a fuzzy complete graph ($F_{C_{om}}G$) if every pair of distinct FVs are adjacent and $\Theta(a) = R(\alpha, \beta)_{a \in \mathfrak{S}^{-1}(\alpha, \beta)}$ for all $\alpha, \beta \in S$.

Definition 1.21. [1] A fuzzy path (F_{P_a}) in a $F_G \Omega = (\Phi, \Theta, \mathfrak{S})$ is an alternating sequence of FVs and FES $(s_0, \Phi(s_0)), (a_1, \Theta(a_1)), (s_1, \Phi(s_1)), (a_2, \Theta(a_2)), (s_2, \Phi(s_2)), \dots, (s_{n-1}, \Phi(s_{n-1})), (a_n, \Theta(a_n)), (s_n, \Phi(s_n))$ such that $\Theta(a_i) > 0$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ and all the FVs are distinct. Here n is called the length of the F_{P_a} . The strength of the F_{P_a} is defined as $\bigcap_{i=1}^n \Theta(a_i)$. In other words the strength of F_{P_a} is defined to be the weight of the weakest F_E of the F_{P_a} . A single $FV \beta$ may also be considered as a F_{P_a} . In this case, the F_{P_a} is of length 0. If a F_{P_a} has length 0, its strength is $\Phi(\beta)$. The consecutive pairs (s_{i-1}, s_i) are called arcs of the F_{P_a} .

Definition 1.22. [1] A closed fuzzy path is called a fuzzy cycle (F_{C_y}) and the length of the fuzzy cycle is given by the number of fuzzy edges in a fuzzy cycle. A fuzzy cycle of length n is denoted as C_n .

Definition 1.23. A $F_G \Omega = (\Phi, \Theta, \mathfrak{S})$ is fuzzy connected graph ($F_{C_{on}}G$) if any two FVs are joined by a F_{P_a} . Otherwise, Ω is called fuzzy disconnected graph ($F_{DC_{on}}G$).

Definition 1.24. Let $\Omega = (\Phi, \Theta, \mathfrak{S})$ be a F_G . The complement of Ω is defined as $\Omega^c = (\Phi^c, \Theta^c, \mathfrak{S})$, where $\Phi^c(\alpha) = \Phi(\alpha)$, for all $\alpha \in S$ and $\Theta^c(a) = \min\{\Phi(\alpha), \Phi(\beta)\} - \Theta(a) \forall a \in L$ and $\mathfrak{S}(a) = (\alpha, \beta)$.

Definition 1.25. A $F_G \Omega = (\Phi, \Theta, \mathfrak{S})$ that has no F_{C_y} s is called a fuzzy cyclic or a forest. A connected forest is called a fuzzy tree (F_T). It is also denoted as f - tree.

Definition 1.26. A $F_G \Omega = (\Phi, \Theta, \mathfrak{S})$ is called a fuzzy bipartite graph (F_{BPG}) if the Φ can be partitioned into two disjoint fuzzy subsets Φ_1 and Φ_2 such that every fuzzy edge of Ω joins a fuzzy point of Φ_1 to a fuzzy point of Φ_2 . The pair (Φ_1, Φ_2) is called a bipartition of Ω .

Definition 1.27. A $F_G \Omega = (\Phi, \Theta, \mathfrak{S})$ is called a fuzzy complete bipartite graph (F_{CBPG}) if the Φ can be partitioned into two disjoint fuzzy subsets Φ_1 and Φ_2 such that every fuzzy point of Φ_1 joins with every fuzzy point of Φ_2 by a fuzzy line and $\Theta(a) = R(\alpha, \beta)_{a \in \mathfrak{S}^{-1}(\alpha, \beta)}$ for all $\alpha \in S_1, \beta \in S_2$. The pair (S_1, S_2) is called a bipartition of S .

The fuzzy complete bipartite graph is denoted as $K_{p,q}$ for p FVs of Φ_1 and q FVs of Φ_2 .

2. FUZZY NUMBER LABELING GRAPH

Definition 2.1. [1] A fuzzy number graceful labeling (F_NGfL) of a $F_G \Omega = (\Phi, \Theta, \mathfrak{S})$ having q FES is an injective mapping $\mathfrak{L} : \Phi(\Omega) \rightarrow \{\tilde{0}, \tilde{1}, \tilde{2}, \dots, \tilde{q}\}$ such that when each $F_E \zeta \zeta$ is assigned the label $|\mathfrak{L}(\zeta) - \mathfrak{L}(\zeta)|$, the resulting F_E labels are distinct. A fuzzy number graceful graph (F_NGfG) is one which admits a F_NGfL .

Definition 2.2. [1] A fuzzy number nearly graceful labeling (F_NNGfL) of a $F_G \Omega = (\Phi, \Theta, \mathfrak{S})$ having p FVs and q FES is an injective mapping $\mathfrak{L} : \Phi(\Omega) \rightarrow \{\tilde{0}, \tilde{1}, \tilde{2}, \dots, \tilde{q} + 1\}$ such that when each $F_E \zeta \zeta$ is assigned the label $|\mathfrak{L}(\zeta) - \mathfrak{L}(\zeta)|$, the resulting F_E labels are distinct. A fuzzy number nearly graceful graph (F_NNGfG) is one which admits a F_NNGfL .

Definition 2.3. [1] A fuzzy number \tilde{m} -graceful labeling ($F_N\tilde{m}GL$) of a $F_G \Omega = (\Phi, \Theta, \mathfrak{S})$ having p FVs and q FES is an injective mapping $\mathfrak{L} : \Phi(\Omega) \rightarrow \{\tilde{0}, \tilde{1}, \tilde{2}, \dots, \tilde{q} + \tilde{m} - 1\}$ such that when each $F_E \zeta \zeta$ is assigned the label $|\mathfrak{L}(\zeta) - \mathfrak{L}(\zeta)|$, the resulting F_E labels are distinct. A fuzzy number \tilde{m} -graceful graph ($F_N\tilde{m}GG$) is one which admits a $F_N\tilde{m}GL$.

Definition 2.4. [1] A fuzzy number one modulo \tilde{m} -graceful labeling of a ${}_F G \Omega = (\Phi, \Theta, \mathfrak{F})$ having p ${}_F V$ s and q ${}_F E$ s is an injective mapping $\mathfrak{L} : \Phi(\Omega) \rightarrow \{ \tilde{0}, \tilde{1}, \tilde{m}, \tilde{m} + 1, 2\tilde{m}, 2\tilde{m} + 1, (\tilde{q} - 1)\tilde{m}, (\tilde{q} - 1)\tilde{m} + 1 \}$ such that when each ${}_F E \zeta\varsigma$ is assigned the label $|\mathfrak{L}(\zeta) - \mathfrak{L}(\varsigma)|$, the resulting ${}_F E$ labels are distinct. A fuzzy number one modulo \tilde{m} -graceful graph is one which admits a fuzzy number one modulo \tilde{m} -graceful labeling.

Definition 2.5. [1] A fuzzy number odd graceful labeling of a ${}_F G \Omega = (\Phi, \Theta, \mathfrak{F})$ having p ${}_F V$ s and q ${}_F E$ s is an injective mapping $\mathfrak{L} : \Phi(\Omega) \rightarrow \{ \tilde{0}, \tilde{1}, \tilde{2}, \dots, 2\tilde{q} - 1 \}$ such that when each ${}_F E \zeta\varsigma$ is assigned the label $|\mathfrak{L}(\zeta) - \mathfrak{L}(\varsigma)|$, the resulting ${}_F E$ labels are distinct. A fuzzy number odd graceful graph is one which admits a fuzzy number odd graceful labeling.

Definition 2.6. [1] A fuzzy number harmonious labeling of a ${}_F G \Omega = (\Phi, \Theta, \mathfrak{F})$ having p ${}_F V$ s and q ${}_F E$ s is an injective mapping \mathfrak{L} from $\Phi(\Omega)$ to the set of integers modulo q such that when each ${}_F E \zeta\varsigma$ is assigned the label $[\mathfrak{L}(\zeta) + \mathfrak{L}(\varsigma)] \pmod{q}$, the resulting ${}_F E$ labels are distinct. A fuzzy number harmonious graph is one which admits a fuzzy number harmonious labeling.

Definition 2.7. [1] A fuzzy number odd harmonious labeling of a ${}_F G \Omega = (\Phi, \Theta, \mathfrak{F})$ having p ${}_F V$ s and q ${}_F E$ s is an injective mapping $\mathfrak{L} : \Phi(\Omega) \rightarrow \{ \tilde{0}, \tilde{1}, \tilde{2}, \dots, 2\tilde{q} - 1 \}$ such that when each ${}_F E \zeta\varsigma$ is assigned the label $[\mathfrak{L}(\zeta) + \mathfrak{L}(\varsigma)]$, the resulting ${}_F E$ labels are distinct. A fuzzy number odd harmonious graph is one which admits a fuzzy number odd harmonious labeling.

Definition 2.8. [1] A fuzzy number even sequential harmonious labeling of a ${}_F G \Omega = (\Phi, \Theta, \mathfrak{F})$ having p ${}_F V$ s and q ${}_F E$ s is an injective mapping $\mathfrak{L} : \Phi(\Omega) \rightarrow \{ \tilde{0}, \tilde{1}, \tilde{2}, \dots, 2\tilde{q} \}$ such that when each ${}_F E \zeta\varsigma$ is assigned the label $[\mathfrak{L}(\zeta) + \mathfrak{L}(\varsigma)]$ if $[\mathfrak{L}(\zeta) + \mathfrak{L}(\varsigma)]$ is even, $[\mathfrak{L}(\zeta) + \mathfrak{L}(\varsigma) + 1]$ if $[\mathfrak{L}(\zeta) + \mathfrak{L}(\varsigma)]$ is odd, the resulting ${}_F E$ labels are distinct. A fuzzy number even sequential harmonious graph is one which admits a fuzzy number even sequential harmonious labeling.

Definition 2.9. [1] A fuzzy number \tilde{m} -odd sequential harmonious labeling of a ${}_F G \Omega = (\Phi, \Theta, \mathfrak{F})$ having p ${}_F V$ s and q ${}_F E$ s is an injective mapping $\mathfrak{L} : \Phi(\Omega) \rightarrow \{ \tilde{m} - 1, \tilde{m}, \tilde{m} + 1, \dots, \tilde{m} + 2\tilde{q} - 2 \}$ such that when each ${}_F E \zeta\varsigma$ is assigned the label $[\mathfrak{L}(\zeta) + \mathfrak{L}(\varsigma)]$ if $[\mathfrak{L}(\zeta) + \mathfrak{L}(\varsigma)]$ is odd, $[\mathfrak{L}(\zeta) + \mathfrak{L}(\varsigma) + 1]$ if $[\mathfrak{L}(\zeta) + \mathfrak{L}(\varsigma)]$ is even, the resulting ${}_F E$ labels are distinct. A fuzzy number \tilde{m} -odd sequential harmonious graph is one which admits a fuzzy number \tilde{m} -odd sequential harmonious labeling.

Definition 2.10. [1] A fuzzy number mean labeling of a ${}_F G \Omega = (\Phi, \Theta, \mathfrak{F})$ having q ${}_F E$ s is an injective mapping $\mathfrak{L} : \Phi(\Omega) \rightarrow \{ \tilde{0}, \tilde{1}, \tilde{2}, \dots, \tilde{q} \}$ such that when each ${}_F E \zeta\varsigma$ is labeled with $[\mathfrak{L}(\zeta) + \mathfrak{L}(\varsigma)] / 2$ if $[\mathfrak{L}(\zeta) + \mathfrak{L}(\varsigma)]$ is even, $[\mathfrak{L}(\zeta) + \mathfrak{L}(\varsigma) + 1] / 2$ if $[\mathfrak{L}(\zeta) + \mathfrak{L}(\varsigma)]$ is odd, the resulting ${}_F E$ labels are distinct. A fuzzy number mean graph is one which admits a fuzzy number mean labeling.

Definition 2.11. [1] A fuzzy number odd mean labeling of a ${}_F G \Omega = (\Phi, \Theta, \mathfrak{F})$ having p ${}_F V$ s and q ${}_F E$ s is an injective mapping $\mathfrak{L} : \Phi(\Omega) \rightarrow \{ \tilde{0}, \tilde{1}, \tilde{2}, \dots, 2\tilde{q} - 1 \}$ such that when each ${}_F E \zeta\varsigma$ is labeled with $[\mathfrak{L}(\zeta) + \mathfrak{L}(\varsigma)] / 2$ if $[\mathfrak{L}(\zeta) + \mathfrak{L}(\varsigma)]$ is even, $[\mathfrak{L}(\zeta) + \mathfrak{L}(\varsigma) + 1] / 2$ if $[\mathfrak{L}(\zeta) + \mathfrak{L}(\varsigma)]$ is odd, the resulting ${}_F E$ labels are distinct. A fuzzy number odd mean graph is one which admits a fuzzy number odd mean labeling.

Definition 2.12. [1] A fuzzy number vertex odd mean labeling of a ${}_F G \Omega = (\Phi, \Theta, \mathfrak{F})$ having p ${}_F V$ s and q ${}_F E$ s is an injective mapping $\mathfrak{L} : \Phi(\Omega) \rightarrow \{ \tilde{1}, \tilde{3}, \tilde{5}, \dots, 2\tilde{q} - 1 \}$ such that when each ${}_F E \zeta\varsigma$ is labeled with $[\mathfrak{L}(\zeta) + \mathfrak{L}(\varsigma)] / 2$, the resulting ${}_F E$ labels are distinct. A fuzzy number vertex odd mean graph is one which admits a fuzzy number vertex odd mean labeling.

Definition 2.13. [1] A fuzzy number vertex even mean labeling of a ${}_F G \Omega = (\Phi, \Theta, \mathfrak{F})$ having p ${}_F V$ s and q ${}_F E$ s is an injective mapping $\mathfrak{L} : \Phi(\Omega) \rightarrow \{ \tilde{2}, \tilde{4}, \tilde{6}, \dots, 2\tilde{q} \}$ such that when each

${}_F E \zeta \varsigma$ is labeled with $[\mathfrak{L}(\zeta) + \mathfrak{L}(\varsigma)] / 2$, the resulting ${}_F E$ labels are distinct. A fuzzy number vertex even mean graph is one which admits a fuzzy number vertex even mean labeling.

Definition 2.14. [1] A fuzzy number square sum labeling of a ${}_F G \Omega = (\Phi, \Theta, \mathfrak{S})$ having p ${}_F V$ s and q ${}_F E$ s is a bijective mapping $\mathfrak{L} : \Phi(\Omega) \rightarrow \{ \tilde{0}, \tilde{1}, \tilde{2}, \dots, \tilde{p} - 1 \}$ such that when each ${}_F E \zeta \varsigma$ is labeled with $[\mathfrak{L}(\zeta)]^2 + [\mathfrak{L}(\varsigma)]^2$, the resulting ${}_F E$ labels are distinct. A fuzzy number square sum graph is one which admits a fuzzy number square sum labeling.

Definition 2.15. [1] A fuzzy number square difference labeling of a ${}_F G \Omega = (\Phi, \Theta, \mathfrak{S})$ having p ${}_F V$ s and q ${}_F E$ s is a bijective mapping $\mathfrak{L} : \Phi(\Omega) \rightarrow \{ \tilde{0}, \tilde{1}, \tilde{2}, \dots, \tilde{p} - 1 \}$ such that when each ${}_F E \zeta \varsigma$ is labeled with $|[\mathfrak{L}(\zeta)]^2 - [\mathfrak{L}(\varsigma)]^2|$, the resulting ${}_F E$ labels are distinct. A fuzzy number square difference graph is one which admits a fuzzy number square difference labeling.

Definition 2.16. [1] A fuzzy number cube sum labeling of a ${}_F G \Omega = (\Phi, \Theta, \mathfrak{S})$ having p ${}_F V$ s and q ${}_F E$ s is a bijective mapping $\mathfrak{L} : \Phi(\Omega) \rightarrow \{ \tilde{0}, \tilde{1}, \tilde{2}, \dots, \tilde{p} - 1 \}$ such that when each ${}_F E \zeta \varsigma$ is labeled with $[\mathfrak{L}(\zeta)]^3 + [\mathfrak{L}(\varsigma)]^3$, the resulting ${}_F E$ labels are distinct. A fuzzy number cube sum graph is one which admits a fuzzy number cube sum labeling.

Definition 2.17. [1] A fuzzy number cube difference labeling of a ${}_F G \Omega = (\Phi, \Theta, \mathfrak{S})$ having p ${}_F V$ s and q ${}_F E$ s is a bijective mapping $\mathfrak{L} : \Phi(\Omega) \rightarrow \{ \tilde{0}, \tilde{1}, \tilde{2}, \dots, \tilde{p} - 1 \}$ such that when each ${}_F E \zeta \varsigma$ is labeled with $|[\mathfrak{L}(\zeta)]^3 - [\mathfrak{L}(\varsigma)]^3|$, the resulting ${}_F E$ labels are distinct. A fuzzy number cube difference graph is one which admits a fuzzy number cube difference labeling.

Definition 2.18. [1] A fuzzy number absolute difference of cubic and square sum labeling of a ${}_F G \Omega = (\Phi, \Theta, \mathfrak{S})$ having p fuzzy points and q ${}_F E$ s is a bijective mapping $\mathfrak{L} : \Phi(\Omega) \rightarrow \{ \tilde{1}, \tilde{2}, \tilde{3}, \dots, \tilde{p} \}$ such that when each ${}_F E \zeta \varsigma$ is labeled with $[[\mathfrak{L}(\zeta)]^3 + [\mathfrak{L}(\varsigma)]^3 - ([\mathfrak{L}(\zeta)]^2 + [\mathfrak{L}(\varsigma)]^2)]$, the resulting ${}_F E$ labels are distinct. A fuzzy number absolute difference of cubic and square sum graph is one which admits a fuzzy number absolute difference of cubic and square sum labeling.

Definition 2.19. [1] A fuzzy number strongly multiplicative labeling of a ${}_F G \Omega = (\Phi, \Theta, \mathfrak{S})$ having p ${}_F V$ s and q ${}_F E$ s is a bijective mapping $\mathfrak{L} : \Phi(\Omega) \rightarrow \{ \tilde{1}, \tilde{2}, \tilde{3}, \dots, \tilde{p} \}$ such that when each ${}_F E \zeta \varsigma$ is labeled with $\mathfrak{L}(\zeta)\mathfrak{L}(\varsigma)$, the resulting ${}_F E$ labels are distinct. A fuzzy number strongly multiplicative graph is one which admits a fuzzy number strongly multiplicative labeling.

Note: $\lfloor n \rfloor$ - The greatest integer less than or equal to n .

$\lceil n \rceil$ - The smallest integer greater than or equal to n .

3. THEOREMS IN FUZZY NUMBER LABELING GRAPH

Definition 3.1. A fuzzy chord of a fuzzy cycle is obtained when two non-adjacent ${}_F V$ s of the fuzzy cycle are joined by an ${}_F E$.

Example 3.2. Consider the figure 3.1.

Fig. 3.1

Here ${}_{\mathbb{F}}E$ of $(w_1,0.3)$ and $(w_8,0.5)$, ${}_{\mathbb{F}}E$ of $(w_2,0.5)$ and $(w_7,0.8)$, ${}_{\mathbb{F}}E$ of $(w_3,0.4)$ and $(w_6,0.5)$ are triangle fuzzy number chords.

Definition 3.3. A fuzzy cycle with parallel fuzzy chords is defined as a ${}_{\mathbb{F}}G \Omega = (\Phi, \Theta, \mathfrak{S})$ obtained by adding the fuzzy chords between the pair of ${}_{\mathbb{F}}Vs (v_1, v_{n-1}), (v_2, v_{n-2}), \dots, (v_{\varpi}, v_{\zeta})$ of the fuzzy cycle $C_n = (v_0, \Phi(v_0))(v_1, \Phi(v_1)) \dots (v_{n-1}, \Phi(v_{n-1})) (v_0, \Phi(v_0))$, $(n \geq 6)$ where $\varpi = \lfloor n/2 \rfloor - 1$, $\zeta = \lfloor n/2 \rfloor + 1$ if n is even, $\zeta = \lfloor n/2 \rfloor + 2$ if n is odd. Then $|\Phi(\Omega)| = n$ and $|\Theta(\Omega)| = \Delta = \frac{3n-3}{2}$ if n is odd, $|\Theta(\Omega)| = \Delta = \frac{3n-2}{2}$ if n is even.

Definition 3.4. Two fuzzy chords of a fuzzy cycle are said to be twin fuzzy chords if they form a triangle with an ${}_{\mathbb{F}}E$ of the fuzzy cycle C_n .

Definition 3.5. Fuzzy bistar graph(${}_{\mathbb{F}}BSG$) is a fuzzy graph obtained from K_2 by joining $t = s+p$ pendant ${}_{\mathbb{F}}Es$ to each end of K_2 . The ${}_{\mathbb{F}}E$ of K_2 is called the central ${}_{\mathbb{F}}E$ of the fuzzy bistar graph and the ${}_{\mathbb{F}}Vs$ of K_2 are called the central ${}_{\mathbb{F}}Vs$ of the fuzzy bistar graph. It is denoted as ${}_{\mathbb{F}}B_{(s,p)}$.

Example 3.6. Consider the fuzzy bistar graph ${}_{\mathbb{F}}B_{(5,4)}$,

Fig. 3.2

Theorem 3.7. Every fuzzy bistar graph is fuzzy number graceful graph.

Proof. Let $\Omega = (\Phi, \Theta, \mathfrak{F})$ be a fuzzy bistar graph with p FVs . That is Ω has p FVs and $p-1 = s+t+1$ FES . Let $\Phi = \{(\omega_0, p_0), (\omega_1, p_1), \dots, (\omega_{p-1}, p_{p-1})\}$

and $\Theta = \{(\eta_1, q_1), (\eta_2, q_2), \dots, (\eta_{p-1}, q_{p-1})\}$ be FVs and FES . One FV of K_2 in the fuzzy bistar graph is adjacent with s FVs and another one FV of K_2 is adjacent with t FVs . Suppose that the one FV (ω_0, p_0) of K_2 is adjacent with $s+1$ FVs , then the mapping \mathcal{L} is defined as $\mathcal{L}(\omega_j, p_j) = \tilde{j}, \tilde{j} = \tilde{0}, \tilde{1}, \tilde{2}, \dots, \tilde{s} + 1$, and the another one FV (ω_1, p_1) of K_2 is adjacent with t pendant FVs , then the mapping \mathcal{L} is defined as $\mathcal{L}(\omega_j, p_j) = \tilde{j}, \tilde{j} = \tilde{s} + 2, \dots, \tilde{p} - 1$, clearly all are distinct, so Ω is a fuzzy number graceful graph.

Example 3.8. A triangle fuzzy number bistar graph with $FB_{(5,4)}$ is given below.

Fig. 3.3

Theorem 3.9. If $\Omega = (\Phi, \Theta, \mathfrak{F})$ is fuzzy number graceful graph with even or odd fuzzy number only, then there exists a partition $\Phi^p = (\Phi^A, \Phi^B)$ of Φ such that the number of FES with one end in Φ^A and the other in Φ^B is $\lceil \frac{p}{2} \rceil$.

Proof. Let $\Omega = (\Phi, \Theta, \mathfrak{F})$ be a fuzzy number graph with even or odd fuzzy number only, of the fuzzy graceful labeling \mathfrak{L} and consider the partition $\Phi^p = (\Phi^A, \Phi^B)$ of Φ such that $\Phi^A = \{h \in \Phi: \mathfrak{L}(h) \equiv 0 \pmod{2}\}$. Since there are $\lceil \frac{p}{2} \rceil$ odd values between 1 and p , and an odd difference is only possible by subtracting an even value from an odd one, the number of fuzzy edges connecting two fuzzy vertices with different parities must be exactly $\lceil \frac{p}{2} \rceil$.

Definition 3.10. A fuzzy caterpillar is a fuzzy tree in which the removal of all fuzzy leaves results in a fuzzy path graph. It is denoted as CA_m , where m is the number of FVs .

Theorem 3.11. All fuzzy number caterpillar trees are fuzzy number graceful graph.

Proof. A fuzzy number caterpillar tree is drawn as a fuzzy number planar bipartite representation and label it as shown in the figure 3.4.

Fig. 3.4

From the figure 3.4, we can prove that every fuzzy number caterpillar tree is a fuzzy number graceful graph.

Example 3.12. A triangle fuzzy number caterpillar tree graph with CA_{10} is given below.

Fig. 3.5

Definition 3.13. If a fuzzy bipartite graph is generalized in a similar fashion, then the fuzzy graph is called fuzzy multipartite graph. Also if a fuzzy complete bipartite graph is generalized in a similar fashion, then the fuzzy graph is called fuzzy complete multipartite graph. It is denoted as $K_{p, q, \dots}$.

Example 3.14. Consider the fuzzy complete multipartite graph $K_{3, 3}$ and $K_{1, 3, 3}$.

Fig. 3.6 - $K_{3,3}$

Fig. 3.7 - $K_{1,3,3}$

Theorem 3.15. The fuzzy complete multipartite graphs $K_{p,q}$, $K_{1,p,q}$, $K_{2,p,q}$, and $K_{1,1,p,q}$ are fuzzy number graceful graphs.

Proof. The following figures say that clearly $K_{p,q}$, $K_{1,p,q}$, $K_{2,p,q}$, and $K_{1,1,p,q}$ are fuzzy number graceful graphs.

Fig. 3.8 - $K_{p,q}$

Fig. 3.9 - $K_{1,3,3}$

Fig. 3.10 - $K_{2,3,3}$

Fig. 3.11 - $K_{1,1,3,3}$

Definition 3.16. The fuzzy wheel graph W_p is the join of a fuzzy cycle graph C_p with a fuzzy singleton graph, i.e., $W_p = C_p + K_1$.

Example 3.17. Consider the fuzzy wheel graphs W_3, W_4 .

Fig. 3.12 – W_3

Fig. 3.13 – W_4

Theorem 3.18. The fuzzy wheel graph $W_k = (\Phi, \Theta, \mathfrak{F})$ is a fuzzy number graceful graph for all $k \geq 3$.

Proof. Let $\Phi = \{ (u_0, p_0), (u_1, p_1), (u_2, p_2), \dots, (v, p) \}$ be the set of FV s, where (v, p) is a FV joined with the fuzzy cycle and consider the following two cases.

Case (i): If $k \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$, then the following formula gives a fuzzy number graceful labeling:

$$\mathfrak{L}(v) \equiv \bar{0} \text{ and } \mathfrak{L}(u_i) \equiv \begin{cases} \overline{2k} & \text{if } i = 0 \\ \bar{2} & \text{if } i = k - 1 \\ \bar{i} & \text{if } i = 1, 3, 5, \dots, k - 3 \\ \overline{2k - i - 1} & \text{if } i = 2, 4, 6, \dots, k - 2. \end{cases}$$

Case (ii): If $k \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$, then the following formula gives a fuzzy number graceful labeling:

$$\mathfrak{L}(v) \equiv \bar{0} \text{ and } \mathfrak{L}(u_i) \equiv \begin{cases} \overline{2k} & \text{if } i = 0 \\ \bar{2} & \text{if } i = 1 \\ \overline{k + i} & \text{if } i = 2, 4, 6, \dots, k - 1 \\ \overline{k + 1 - i} & \text{if } i = 3, 5, 7, \dots, k - 2. \end{cases}$$

CONCLUSION

Fuzzy number graceful labeling is one of the main branch in fuzzy graph. Here different types of graceful labeling definition is given, and some theorems are stated and proved. Using the above definitions and theorems, we can find more results. It can be extended into different types of fuzzy number graceful labeling.

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